

PHOTOCHEMICAL AFTER-EFFECT IN THE OXALATE IODINE REACTION

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The after-effect rate in the oxalate-iodine reaction increases with the length of period of pre-illumination. The shapes of the curves obtained indicate that the after-effect rate of reaction is identical with the photochemical rate at the instant of darkening. It falls off very rapidly at first, so that it has already been largely reduced by the time the first reading is taken. The duration of the after-effect, *i.e.*, period during which a measurable falling velocity can be detected by the disappearance of I_2 , is independent of temperature and period of pre-illumination. The end-rates, when the fall in velocity becomes very slow, are found to be at a higher level than the normal dark reaction to an extent depending upon the period of pre-illumination. The value of the "secondary after-effect" obtained by adding fresh iodine in the dark to solutions in which all the original iodine has been used up by exposure to light is diminished (a) with increase of the time interval between decolourisation and addition of iodine, (b) with increase of temperature and (c) with increase of concentration of KI. In the absence of iodine the "activity" disappears completely in the course of time depending upon the temperature.

Solutions of free oxalic acid and iodine react photochemically but there is no after-effect. Mixtures of oxalate (or oxalic acid) and iodine from which all the molecular iodine has been removed photochemically do not reduce mercuric chloride, indicating the absence of "activated oxalic acid" in the sense in which the term has been applied in the permanganate-oxalate reaction. A mechanism has been suggested dispensing with assumptions about the existence of activated molecules, and depending solely upon a simple extension of the Berthoud chain mechanism for the oxalate-iodine photo-reaction.

The object of this investigation was to try and examine, if only from a phenomenal point of view, whether there is any relation between the after-effect in the potassium oxalate-iodine reaction, and the so-called "activation" of oxalic acid by the addition of small quantities of potassium permanganate to it in aqueous solution. It is only natural to suppose that these two reactions may have a common origin, namely, that light energy absorbed in the first instance, or chemical energy liberated by the primary act of oxidation in the second, may be transferred to oxalic acid molecules or ions, conferring upon them the enhanced reactivity shown, for example, in their behaviour with mercuric chloride in the latter instance.

The apparent close parallelism between the two has been further emphasised by the observations of Abel (*Z. Elektrochem.*, 1937, **43**, 629) that a mixture of potassium oxalate and iodine after having been decolourised by illumination shows enhanced reactivity towards iodine subsequently added in the dark, over and above the normal dark rate. The question arises whether such end solutions may not also contain some form of activated product identical with or similar to that produced in

the permanganate-oxalic acid reaction. The latter will be the subject of a further communication.

The following account shows the results which have been obtained from a more detailed study of the after-effect in potassium oxalate-iodine-potassium iodide mixtures under varying degrees of concentration and temperature.

Effect of Time of Illumination.

There is a measurable dark reaction between potassium oxalate and iodine which has been found by previous workers to be unimolecular with respect to iodine. On illumination of solutions with the light of a 500-watt filament lamp for a short time, we find that a marked after-effect is produced, the initial rate of which increases continuously with the time of pre-illumination.

Table I shows the course of an experiment in detail. First readings for the after-effect were taken as soon as practicable after darkening. In all cases, the corresponding dark rate has been subtracted from the total effect to give the after-effect rate. For the calculation of the velocity constants for the after-effect, zero time has been reckoned from the moment the first reading was taken after cutting off the illumination. The pre-illuminated reaction mixtures were always shaken before taking the first observation in the dark.

TABLE I.

Temperature of thermostat = 50°. Concentrations: $N/2\text{-K}_2\text{C}_2\text{O}_4$, $N/30\text{-KI}$, $N/120\text{-I}_2$.

$K = 1/t \log a/a-x$, where a is the initial concentration of iodine and $a-x$ is the concentration at time t .

A. Dark reaction.			B. Illuminated at the point marked.*		
Time.	$\text{Na}_2\text{S}_2\text{O}_3$	$K \times 10^6$.	Time.	$\text{Na}_2\text{S}_2\text{O}_3$.	$K \times 10^6$.
0 min.	8.10 c.c.	—	0 min.	8.00 c.c.	—
66	7.45	550	68	7.35	541
120	6.90	582	120	6.90	536
180	6.40	568	180	6.30	576
245	5.95	547	190* - 205 l.e.,	15 min.	illumination
300	5.45	574			$K \times 10^6$.
435	4.65	554	205	4.95	—
540	4.00	567	225	3.35	413
			250	3.20	228
			308	2.80	156
			441	1.90	139
			540	2.40	138
			685	0.95	131

Table II shows the effect of time of illumination at 50°. The initial concentrations of the reactants were the same as in Table I.

TABLE II.

Time of illumination.							
15 min.		10 min.		5 min.		1 min.	
<i>t.</i>	After-effect $K \times 10^5$.	<i>t.</i>	$K \times 10^5$.	$K \times 10^5$.	$K \times 10^5$.	<i>t.</i>	$K \times 10^5$.
0 min.	...	0 min.	...	0 min.	...	0 min.	...
20	357	21	173	25	68	30	40
45	172	50	105	95	33	88	24
103	100	111	64	231	26	271	19
236	83	231	42	345	19	374	18
335	82	360	38	480	15	480	10
480	75	478	34				

These results are illustrated in Fig. 1. The curves show that the after-effect is a function of the total light energy absorbed during illumination *i.e.*, number of molecules of reactant transformed. It drops off extremely rapidly the instant the light is cut off. Tables III and IV summarise the results obtained at 25°.

TABLE III.

Temperature of thermostat = 25°. Concentrations: $N/2-K_2C_2O_4$, $N/300-KI$, $N/1200-I_2$.

A. Dark reaction.

B. Illuminated for 15 min. and then measured the rates in the dark.

Time.	$Na_2S_2O_3$.	$K \times 10^7$.	Time.	$Na_2S_2O_3$.	$K \times 10^6$.
0 min.	7.15 c.c.	...	0 min.	1.00 cc.	...
55	7.10	545	10	0.85	706
180	7.00	511	53	0.60	418
314	6.85	584	99	0.40	402
451	6.75	554	140	0.30	374
			197	0.20	355

Table IV shows the effect of time of illumination at 25°. The initial concentrations of the reactants were the same as in Table III.

TABLE IV.

Time of illumination.							
15 min.		10 min.		5 min.		1 min.	
	After-effect $K \times 10^6$.	t .	$K \times 10^6$.	t .	$K \times 10^6$.	t .	$K \times 10^6$.
0 min.	...	0 min.	...	0 min.	...	0 min.	...
10	701	15	215	15	99	15	41
53	413	30	183	43	81	33	36
99	397	60	163	88	63	73	28
140	369	120	146	186	54	123	23
197	350	240	116	315	47	242	17
				426	39	381	16
						557	12

TABLE V.

Concentrations were the same as in Table III. The dark reaction at this temperature was immeasurably slow. Exposure to bright sunlight for 30 min. Temperature of thermostat = 0.3°.

Time (min.)	...	0	97	212	312	481
After-effect ($K \times 10^7$)	—		917	679	519	451

The figures show that there is a regular fall in the after-effect which persists for a long period. They are calculated on the unimolecular formula which holds for the normal dark reaction, but this formula is not applicable to the actual course of the after-reaction, which probably depends upon the slow disappearance of some active intermediate product. The latter may react with iodine to give the measured after-effect while decaying spontaneously in other ways. It is thus impossible to represent the total change by any simple formula. For this reason the measured rate of iodine reduction (Fig. 1) never approaches that of the normal dark reaction within the measurable time limits of the experiments.

FIG. 1

Photochemical after-effect at 50°

Curves 1-4 show the course of after-effect obtained in the periods of illumination of 15, 10, 5 and 1 minute respectively. Conc. same as in Table I.

FIG. 2

Photochemical after-effect at 0.3°

The conc. of the reactants same as in Table IV.

The effect of different temperatures cannot be usefully compared since different concentrations of iodine and potassium iodide must be employed in order to obtain convenient reaction velocities. The latter can be regulated by varying the concentrations of potassium iodide.

It is worthy of note that no measurable dark reaction was found

at 0.3° , and the after-effect curve obtained (Fig. 2) thus represents the rate of decay without this complication.

Effect of Addition of Fresh Iodine to Decolourised End Solutions of Illuminated $K_2C_2O_4 - I_2$.

We have examined in detail the effect of restoring in the dark in the original concentration the iodine completely used up in the photo-reaction (i) at various time intervals after decolourisation of the mixture, (ii) at various temperatures and (iii) with varying concentrations of potassium iodide.

For the sake of brevity the tables are not reproduced. The results of experiments on (i) at 25° are shown in Fig. 3.

FIG. 3
Secondary after-effect at 25° .

The curves A-H show the course of secondary after-effect obtained by the addition of fresh iodine to the solutions in which iodine had been completely reduced photochemically, immediately after the reduction had been judged to be complete and intervals of 15 mins., 30 mins., one hour, one hour 40 mins., 3 hours, 6 hours, and 12 hours from the moment of decolourisation of the original solutions respectively. After an interval of 24 hours the secondary after-effect vanished and the addition of fresh iodine to this solution gave the normal dark rate of the reaction. The concentrations were the same as in Table IV.

(i) *Effect of Time Interval.*—It will be seen that “decay curves” are obtained similar in form to the original after-effect curves, but that the actual values of the initial velocity constants are very much less than those obtained by illumination.

In these experiments fresh iodine was added in the dark at different intervals from the moment after the original illuminated iodine had been judged to have been used up. The estimation of the actual intervals is therefore only approximate. The reaction velocities obtained indicate that there is a general spontaneous decay of activity in the decolourised solution extending over a period of about 24 hours, after which it is no longer detectable.

(ii) *Effect of Temperature.*—Experiments were performed at various temperatures between 25° and 50° on the "activity" of the decolourised solution, using the same concentrations of reactants in each case.

TABLE VI.

Concentrations: $N/2\text{-K}_2\text{C}_2\text{O}_4$, $N/300\text{-KI}$, $N/1200\text{-I}_2$.

Temperature.	Dark rate. $K_1 \times 10^6$.	Rate with added I_2 . $K_2 \times 10^6$.	Activity K_2/K_1 .
25°C	5	35	7.0
30	17	82	4.8
35	45	180	4.0
40	127	287	2.3
45	297	354	1.2
50	770	779	1.0

In all these experiments fresh iodine was added as soon as the decolourisation of the original mixture by illumination had been judged to be complete. The measure of "activity" has been taken as the ratio of the rate of iodine reduction, obtained one hour after the addition of fresh iodine to the decolourised solution, to the normal dark rate at a particular temperature. The rate of disappearance of added iodine, which we may call the "secondary after-effect", has been computed in the above manner in order to obtain comparable results. The data clearly show that the rate of disappearance of "activity" is a function of the temperature. It is greatest at 25°, gradually diminishing up to about 50° when no measurable effect could be detected.

A significant fact is that at 50° there is still a pronounced photochemical after-effect (Table IA and IB) in solutions partially decolourised by illumination, but that no secondary after-effect can be observed on adding fresh iodine in the dark. The "activity" has disappeared within the short interval between decolourisation and addition of fresh iodine in the dark.

(iii) *Effect of Potassium iodide Concentration.*—This is shown in Table VII where the values of the initial velocity constants after one hour from the moment of addition of fresh iodine are tabulated at four concentrations of potassium iodide. The "activity" of the decolourised solutions is seen to diminish with increasing concentrations of the latter. Potassium

iodide exerts a common inhibiting effect on (i) the normal dark reaction, (ii) the photochemical rate, as pointed out by Berthoud (*Helv. Chim. Acta*, 1924, 7, 307), (iii) the photochemical after-effect, and (iv) the secondary after-effect.

TABLE VII.

Temperature = 30°. Concentrations : $N/2\text{-K}_2\text{C}_2\text{O}_4$, $N/1200\text{-I}_2$.

Conc. of KI	...	$N/300$	$N/150$	$N/100$	$N/75$
Sec. after-effect ($K_2 \times 10^5$)...	64		17	11	2

Effect of Addition of KI on the Photochemical After-effect.

The maximum photochemical after-effect was obtained in solutions containing no potassium iodide initially as shown in Table VIII.

TABLE VIII.

Temperature of thermostat = 25°. Concentrations : $N/2\text{-K}_2\text{C}_2\text{O}_4$, $N/1080\text{-I}_2$ (No potassium iodide).

A. Dark reaction.			B. Illuminated at the point marked.*			
Time.	$\text{Na}_2\text{S}_2\text{O}_3$	$K \times 10^5$	Time.	$\text{Na}_2\text{S}_2\text{O}_3$	$K \times 10^5$	After-effect $K \times 10^5$
0 min.	11'95 c.c.	...	0 min.	12'00 c.c.
33	11'00	109	60	10'40	104	...
120	8'50	123	90	9'25	126	...
180	7'50	112	137'5*—142'5	<i>i.e.</i> , 5 min. illumination.		
210	7'10	108	142'5	2'10
240	6'75	103	145	1'75	3168	3062
272	6'50	97	150	1'70	1226	1118
308	6'35	89	166	1'40	749	643
			183	1'05	743	637
			210	0'50	545	439

From the tables,

$$\frac{\text{After effect } (t=145 \text{ min.})}{\text{Dark rate } (t=145 \text{ min.})} = \frac{3062}{116} = 26, \text{ approximately,}$$

whereas from Table IV, for the same time of pre-illumination, *i.e.*, 5 minutes this ratio is $\frac{99}{5} = 20$ (approx.).

Thus the presence of *N*/300-KI in the latter case diminishes the relative value of the after-effect. The decreasing values of the velocity constants in Table VIIIA are due to the gradual accumulation of potassium iodide in the solution.

Free Oxalic Acid and Iodine.

Attempts were made finally to examine the reaction between free oxalic acid and iodine under nitrogen using the same source of illumination. Some measurements have appeared in the literature of the oxalic acid-iodine reaction performed in air. These are of little value on account of the photochemical reaction between aqueous HI and atmospheric oxygen. The extent to which the reaction can be examined is limited, firstly, by the small solubility of iodine in aqueous solution and secondly, by the slowness of the reaction, but it was found possible, using *N*/800-iodine, to obtain a measureable dark rate at 50° (Table IX).

TABLE IX.

Temp. of thermostat = 50°. Concentrations : *N*/2-H₂C₂O₄, *N*/800-I₂ (without KI).

A. Dark reaction.			B. Illuminated for 30 min.		
Time.	Na ₂ S ₂ O ₃ .	<i>K</i> × 10 ⁷	Time	Na ₂ S ₂ O ₃ .	<i>K</i> × 10 ⁷
0 min.	3'40 c.c.	...	0 min.	2'20 c.c.	...
100	3'35	650	170	2'15	588
360	3'25	545	355	2'10	577
483	3'20	547	500	2'08	506

A distinct photo-rate was found superimposed on the dark reaction which could not be measured accurately with the resources at our disposal, but it is significant that no after-effect could be observed. These latter

His theory does not offer any explanation for the absence of the secondary after-effect at higher temperatures found by us, when the photochemical after-effect is still quite pronounced.

It appears to us that a possible scheme may be derived by a simple extension of Berthoud's chain mechanism for the photochemical reaction (*loc. cit.*) as shown below.

Both I and $\text{C}_2\text{O}_4'$ are chain carriers and since they are assumed to be in very small stationary concentrations in the presence of a large excess of $\text{C}_2\text{O}_4''$ and I_2 , their chances of reaction will be overwhelmingly predominant. So long as molecular iodine is present, reaction (v) will proceed slowly as revealed in the after-effect.

If we assume that in the absence of molecular iodine reaction (iv) is an instantaneously established equilibrium reaction, depending upon electronic interchange, we may write it in the form

When fresh iodine is added to (vi) the chain is recommenced, thus accounting for the secondary after-effect.

The respective stationary concentrations of $\text{C}_2\text{O}_4'$ and I are mainly reduced by self-combination, the rate of which increases with rise of temperature

but the chances of these reactions are small compared to (iv) and (v).

The decay of "activity" may be attributed to the falling stationary concentration of $\text{C}_2\text{O}_4'$ in (vii) and consequent lower reaction velocity of (v), which is responsible for the removal of molecular iodine.

The increase in the after-effect rate with increasing periods of pre-illumination can be accounted for by assuming (v) to be slower than (iv), so that an excess of $\text{C}_2\text{O}_4'$ accumulates during illumination.

The fact that no secondary after-effect has been found at 50° may be explained on the assumption that the chances of reaction (vii) will be very much greater in the absence of I_2 , and it is so fast at that temperature that the stationary concentration of C_2O_4' in (vi) becomes negligible and hence no change is observed when fresh iodine is added in the dark. With increasing time intervals before addition of iodine at lower temperature, the concentration of C_2O_4' will have been correspondingly reduced.

The same explanation holds good for the lower rate of the secondary after-effect compared to the photochemical after-effect.

The effect of addition of potassium iodide, in extension of Berthoud's original assumption for the photochemical mechanism, is to reduce the stationary concentration of I and hence of C_2O_4' in (vi) in accordance with reaction (iii). The concentration of C_2O_4 (i) is highest in light when a constant supply of fresh iodine atoms is being furnished, (ii) falls off rapidly on darkening owing to self-combination, (iii) is small when iodine is completely used up, (iv) is minimum after about 24 hours.

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